

Reattachment of a Vertical Complicated Subgingival Crown Root Fracture Followed by MTA Pulpotomy in an Immature Central Incisor; A Case Report with Follow up

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Abstract

Coronal fractures of the anterior teeth frequently occur in children and adolescents. When the fractured tooth fragment is available and there is minimal or no disruption to the biological width, reattaching the fragment is a viable management option. This method preserves the tooth's original anatomy, colour and texture, offering excellent and durable esthetic results. It also restores functionality, enhances psychological well-being, and is a straightforward procedure. For optimal outcomes, patient cooperation and awareness of the treatment's limitations are crucial.

Keywords: coronal fracture, biological width, reattachment.

Introduction

Injuries to the oral region account for approximately 5% of all physical injuries,¹ with around 92% of patients seeking consultation for oral injuries presenting with traumatic dental injuries (TDIs). The most commonly reported dental injury is a crown fracture in the maxillary anterior teeth, particularly among preschool children and adolescents.^{2,3} TDIs can have significant physical, psychological, and social impacts, generally affecting the patient's quality of life. Consequently, dental injuries require prompt emergency intervention and management, focusing on restoring both the function and aesthetics of the fractured tooth.

The management of crown fractures depends on several factors, including the type of fracture (complicated or uncomplicated), the degree and pattern of the fracture, the patient's age, and the stage of tooth eruption.⁴ Various treatment options are available for restoring a fractured tooth, such as full coverage crowns, post and core procedures, and composite restorations. With the development of advanced adhesive systems, tooth fragment reattachment-which was once considered a temporary solution-has now become an established treatment modality.^{5,6} The first documented case of tooth fragment reattachment was reported by Chosack and Eidelman in 1964.⁷

Tooth fragment reattachment is indicated when the fractured segment is available and fits well with the remaining tooth structure. This technique offers

numerous advantages:

- The original color, contour, and texture of the tooth are preserved.
- It is a highly conservative procedure, often requiring little or no tooth preparation.
- The wear rate of the incisal edge is similar to that of the adjacent tooth, unlike composite restorations, which tend to wear down more quickly.
- The procedure is relatively simple and requires less chairside time.
- Patients with TDIs often experience negative psychological effects; reattachment provides a quick and effective outcome, boosting overall optimism and confidence.
- It is a cost-effective option compared to more comprehensive treatments.^{8,9}

Prosthetic restoration in younger patients can be challenging due to factors like larger pulpal sizes, ongoing tooth eruption, and gingival margin instability. The advent of composite resins has expanded the possibilities for various treatment approaches. When an intact tooth fragment is available, reattachment may offer the most functional and esthetic solution. This approach represents one of the most favorable applications of adhesive restorative dentistry.¹⁰

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Case Report

A 10-year-old healthy male patient with no significant medical history visited the Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry at Career Post Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Lucknow. The primary complaint was trauma to the upper front tooth that occurred 15 days prior. The patient reported that the injury happened when he fell down the stairs and struck the floor, resulting in bleeding from the tooth at the time of the accident. He had taken over-the-counter analgesics for pain relief. The patient was well-oriented to person, place, and time, and there was no history of vomiting. On examination, the upper right central incisor showed a vertical complicated crown-root fracture extending from the center of incisal edge going up to and beyond the cervical line subgingivally (Figs 1 and 2). Pulp vitality test showed early response of 21 and all the other teeth responded within normal limits.

Fig. -1

Fig. -2

The fractured fragment showed grade 3 mobility while the remaining part of tooth structure was firm. The involved tooth was tender on vertical percussion however occlusion was unaffected. Radiographic examination of the upper anterior region revealed the fracture line in upper left central incisor passing from its incisal edge, through the pulp and extending into the cervical one third of the root. Periapical area showed nollas stage 9irt 21(Fig 3). Based on the clinical and radiographic examination, a diagnosis of reversible pulpitis was made.

Fig. -3

Various treatment modalities were explained to the parents of the child with their pros and cons and it was finally decided to go with the present treatment approach. Preparation of the operation site was done by scrubbing with 2% povidone-Iodine solution and profound anesthesia was achieved by administering 2% Lignocaine with Adrenaline (1:200000). The fractured fragment was detached from the main tooth structure by separating the gingival attachment with no. 15 BP blade (Fig.4, 5).

Fig. -4

Fig. -5

The fractured fragment was then cleaned of debris and kept soaked in normal saline. It measured about 3-4 mm below cemento enamel junction. Crown lengthening was done to expose the fracture margin The subgingival exten-

sions of the main tooth structure and the fractured fragment were left untouched for the purpose of a guide to the reattachment. The fractured fragment and the main tooth were cleaned using pumice and water slurry. MTA pulpotomy done followed by sealing the access cavity with composite restoration. Surfaces of the fractured fragment and the main tooth structure were etched with 34% phosphoric acid gel (Dentsply, USA) for 15 seconds, washed and dried moist (Fig. 6,7).

Fig. -6

Fig. -7

Later they were coated with Prime and Bond NT (Dentsply, USA) with the help of applicator tip and cured for 20 seconds. The fractured fragment was bonded to the remaining tooth structure with the help of the microfilled anterior composite (Clearfill, Kuraray, Japan) which was photo polymerized as per the instructions of the manufacturer.

Fig. -8

Fig. -9

Fig. -10

Discussion

Treating a young permanent tooth with an open apex can be particularly challenging for dentists. In this case, the patient exhibited a complicated crown-root fracture accompanied by mobility of the coronal fragment. According to the guidelines set by the International Association of Dental Traumatology (IADT), the recommended management for a complicated crown-root fracture includes stabilizing the coronal fragment, performing an endodontic procedure, and placing a post-retained crown.¹¹

For successful reattachment, several factors need to be considered, including the fracture site, the size of the fractured fragment, pulpal involvement, root maturity, periodontal status, biological width invasion, occlusion, and the choice of reattachment material. If the fragment remains dehydrated for an extended period, the tooth's strength can be compromised. Rehydrating the tooth fragment can enhance its resistance, as dentin dehydration leads to the collapse of collagen fibers, hindering the proper penetration of resin monomers, which in turn weakens adhesion between the dentin and composite. In this case, the patient arrived at the department immediately after the trauma with the fractured segment intact, reducing the likelihood of dehydration.¹²

And reasen and Andreasen suggested that reattaching a fractured segment can serve as a temporary treatment option for preteens or teenagers, allowing definitive treatment to be delayed until the gingival margin contours have become relatively stable.¹³ Excessive forces if used during orthodontic extrusion of roots can lead to pain, failure of the tooth to move, root damage, tilting of the abutment teeth and subsequent impaction of the root being extruded so this treatment option was ruled out by the parents.¹⁴ As the reattachment procedure does not preclude any future treatment so whenever an intact fragment is available, reattachment of fractured

fragment should be considered as a viable first treatment option.¹⁰ Liew too described the prognosis of this procedure as it can act as a short to medium-term temporary restoration which has the potential for indefinite service.¹⁵ Therefore the narrated approach was opted.

This case involved reattaching the tooth with no preparation technique. As per Shirani et al., reattachment of the fragment with no preparation technique and adequate rehydration resulted in higher bond strength.^{16,17} Studies by Worthington et al. and Davari and Sadeghi found that reattached teeth with added preparations such as bevels, over contour, and the internal grooves do not provide better bond strength than that of no preparation technique.¹⁸

Although using a rubber dam for isolation creates an environment favorable for quality adhesive dentistry, it was not used in this case because the fracture line was too subgingival. Applying a rubber dam clamp could have caused excessive, uncontrolled bleeding from the soft tissues. Instead, other isolation methods, such as cotton rolls, 2 × 2 gauze, high vacuum suction, and a hemostatic agent, were employed. The longevity of the reattachment remains uncertain before a final permanent restoration, such as a suitable extracoronary restoration, is placed.

Fig. -11

Fig. -12

Conclusion

Although the reattachment is susceptible to the effects of cyclic fatigue and hydrolytic degradation over time, various studies have described functional and esthetic successes exceeding 7 years.¹⁰ The prognosis of reattachment procedure further needs to be assessed in long term clinical studies. In the present case “Patient came for the follow-up at the end of the third month (Figs 11 and 12).

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